

(Grant Agreement 101093921)

D5.2 – Annex II

Step-by-step workplan for each event - template

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HORIZON-MISS-2021-CLIMA-02-05 - Local engagement of citizens in the co-creation of societal transformational change for climate resilience

European Citizen Science Association

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Adaptation AGORA- Peer-to-Peer Learning Workshop #XX

Hosts: ICLEI (main)

Objective(s) of the event

- The objectives for the XXX peer-to-peer learning workshops are:
- The target group:
- Language:

Details and roles

Title:

Speaker(s) (1 max 2):

Time:

Registration link:

Meeting link:

Main facilitator(s):

Technical support:

- Starting the meeting
- Giving co-host rights to XXX
- Letting the audience in at XX
- Starting the recording
- Pin all speakers for the panel discussion
- Share the links
- Mute participants, general order keeping, etc. if needed

To-dos

What?	By when?	Who?	Status
Agenda draft for the workshop			
Invite speakers (save the dates earlier)			
Determine title, write description and plan dissemination			
Set up Teams meeting link			
Set up Teams registration form following these AGORA guidelines for webinars			
Send invitations to register for the live session			
Host the session <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitation • Technical support • Recording the session 			
Write summary report (see template)			
Steps from “follow-up plan” below			

Dissemination plan

To-dos BEFORE the event: who does what? by when?

- Define title and description of session
- Define agenda for the workshop
- Invite speakers
- Set up Teams meeting link giving co-organiser roles as needed
- Set up Teams registration form following these [AGORA guidelines for webinars](#)
- Prepare text for email to followers
- Prepare text for website newsbit
- Write small text for social media - ICLEI
- Prepare sharepics / visuals that other partners can share (both with and without “save the date) – APRE
- Disseminate event following steps below

Dissemination steps: when?

- Twitter posts
 - 1st: Save the date
 - 2nd post approaching the event
- LinkedIn posts
 - 1st: Save the date
 - 2nd post approaching the event
- Newsletter item
- Newsbit for AGORA website
- **Community Hub Forum Post to open registrations**
 - We'll start by creating an editable Forum Post to announce and communicate details about the upcoming event.
 - create an "Event" entry for the next Peer Learning event. It will be shown as an "upcoming event" on the Hub.
- Email to followers (APRE), also to include followers more closely:
 - Approx one month before event (or more, if possible)
 - Asking if someone would like to contribute as a speaker
 - Include small survey gathering ideas pre-event
 - Include follow-up from previous event (see "Follow up plan" below)
- Each partner sending invitation to own network
- Email to participants of previous event

Follow-up – AFTER THE EVENT

- Upload recording to Youtube
- Write Summary report using the template
- Upload content on Community Hub – based on SEI instructions and [this guidance for creating content](#) on the CH:
 - Update Forum Post conversation within the existing "Cities and Climate Change" theme using specific topic titles
 - Create an "Event" entry (left-up corner under "new") and add all relevant info based on the report, including recording and material (e.g. slides)
 - SEI add the URL of the Event we created under the Pilot Pin
 - We will copy the URL of the Event into the Forum Post previously created and update it with the results of the exchange + including the YouTube link
- Create news article on Adaptation AGORA website (based on the report) including link to video on YouTube
- Based on news article, create social media post to promote YouTube recording
- Download list of effective participants and upload to Teams folder
- Update list of participants including those that registered via email communication, to have the full list to be used for future communication (incl. follow-up email)
- Send out follow-up email to registered people and participants
- Send out follow-up email to followers (which is the invitation email to the next event --> see "Dissemination plan" above)

Items to include in follow-up email to participants and registered people

- Link to recording on Youtube
- Slides
- Sign up to newsletter
- Invitation to sign up for the Community Hub because the conversation continues there in-between the other events → Link to discussion forum on Community Hub
- Information to become followers
- Save the date about next event

Important things to consider

Notes about participants and registrations:

- Add clause that allows us to contact people after the event
 - E.g. ‘I agree to be contacted by email for the next events in the series and for other events of the Adaptation AGORA project’.
 - Check with WP2/WP3 to broaden also by adding an invitation to interact with academies, or potentially the future release of the App, you can also specify that type of communication (and I would say it would be interesting to take advantage of and further involve these types of stakeholders, and it would certainly be very positive for some of them to know about our digital tools in detail).

During the session

- During the first event (starting at 11:00) most participants logged in at 11:05 and kept joining until 11:15. Leave the first 5 minutes to welcome participants and wait to start the presentation
- Select setting muting participants as they enter the meeting
 - Check how to unmute them to allow for discussion
- Reflect how to make it more relaxed / foster dialogue
 - Perhaps 1 h and a half and discussion in breakout groups?
 - How to foster actual peer-learning?

Agenda

Time	Session title	Format and description	Facilitator/lead/speaker(s)
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15 min before start	Waiting room		
2 min	Welcome	Introducing the speaker(s), agenda, rules of engagement, etc.	
3 min	Getting to know each other	1-2 poll questions	
15 min	Keynote	Presentation/general introduction of the topic	
30	Moderated discussion	Q&A with all the participants	
5 min	Wrap up	Share relevant material/resources for the session	

Report template

Title	
Location, Region or Focus Area	
Details	
Speaker(s)	
Moderators	
Participants	
Objective of the session	
Structure of the session	
Summary of session’s content	
Main Learnings	
Resources shared	
Reflections for improvement of P2P learning process	

